

Properties of *N*-Fatty-amine Salts and their Aqueous Solutions

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Alternation of melting point in the alkylamine acetate and propionate series occurs so also in alkyl amine series, like for fatty acid series. The nature of alkyl chain, i.e. whether even or odd, appears to influence micellisation characteristics of the salts.

THE sodium salts of odd- and even-chain fatty acids behave as separate homologous series in aqueous solutions, based on the observed pattern of their critical micelle concentration (CMC)¹. To ascertain the behaviour of cationic surfactants, the present investigation on amine salts was taken up.

Experimental

Preparation of amines and their salts: Glc-pure *n*-alkylamines having even number of C atoms, namely, dodecyl-, tetradecyl-, hexadecyl- and octadecyl- amines, were all obtained by repeated vacuum fractional distillation of the commercially available cocount and hydrogenated tallow amines.

The odd-chain *n*-alkylamines were prepared by Schmidt reaction, from glc-pure even-chain fatty acids through azides² and purified by vacuum fractional distillation; the determined amine values³ agreed with the theoretical values and tlc analysis did not show any impurities.

Acetic and propionic acid salts of the pure amines were prepared according to the procedure of Ralston *et al.*⁴; the longer chain amine salts crystallised out at room temperature while, the lower homologues at 15°. The salts were recrystallised till the absence of the free amine spot in tlc analysis. The salts were dried under reduced pressure and kept in a dessicator. The samples had a

purity of 99.5–100% when tested according to the procedure of Babcock *et al.*⁵.

Determination of properties: The melting points (m.p.) were determined by closed capillary method.

The temperature at which an aqueous 1% solution of amine salt (kept in a water-bath that was slowly heated) became clear was noted; this is called Krafft point (K.P.).

The data of CMC at 30° (Table 1) were obtained by the conductivity method⁶. The point of inflection in the plots of specific conductance against concentration is taken as CMC. The given values agree closely with those obtained from the points of inflection of the plots of surface tension of solutions against log concentration of the compounds as well as with those obtained by dye method.

Results and Discussion

Melting behaviour: The determined values of m.p. of *N*-alkylamines, their acetate and propionate salts reasonably agree with the reported values (Table 1), while some of them are being reported for the first time. With the exception of dodecylamine acetate, the m.p. increases with the increasing alkyl chain length by a CH₂ group. The m.p. data, when represented graphically, give an interesting picture (Fig. 1); for the purpose of comparison, the data

TABLE 1—PROPERTIES OF ALKYL AMINES AND THEIR SALTS

No. of C-atoms in alkyl chain	M.p.(°C)*			K.P.(°C)		CMC (mmol dm ⁻³)	
	Amines	Amine acetates	Amine propionates	Amine acetates	Amine propionates	Amine acetates	Amine propionates
11	16.9(16.5)	54.2	40.5	<0	<0	14.60	29.60
12	23.1(23.3)	69.1(68–69)	56.6(56–57)	<0	<0	12.30	8.84
13	29.6(27.0)	66.2(66–68)	57.4	<0	<0	4.23	7.65
14	38.4(38.2)	75.2(74–76)	67.2	12.1	13.8	3.34	2.09
15	40.2(–)	75.8(75–77)	69.3	25.1	26.2	1.189	2.00
16	46.5(46.8)	81.4(80–81)	75.0	45.4	47.5	0.915	0.529
17	48.7(49.0)	82.1(81–83)	76.5	70.6	74.5	0.335	0.504
18	52.8(53.1)	84.5(84–86)	79.9(78–79)	77.5	80.5	0.253	0.131

*Figures in parenthesis are reported m.p. data for alkyl amines (Ref. 7), their acetates (Ref. 8) and propionates (Ref. 9).

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Fig. 1. Plots of m.p. against number of carbon atoms in the chain: (FA) fatty acids, (AM) alkyl amines, (ACE) alkylamine acetates and (PRO) alkylamine propionates.

reported earlier from this laboratory¹ are also represented. Like fatty acids, the three homologous series of compounds exhibit alternation of m.p. as the series are ascended. The *n*-alkylamines have lower m.p. than the fatty acids having the same number of C-atoms, while acetate salts have much higher m.p. The propionate salts have, surprisingly, m.p. between those of the corresponding amine salts and the parent amines. The shape of the curves also shows that the differences in m.p. of the adjacent homologues in a given series decrease as the series is ascended. Further, the trend of convergence of the lines of odd- and even-chain derivatives indicates that at higher alkyl chain length, the difference in closeness of packing of these compounds in solid state becomes somewhat smaller.

Solubility: The salts of amines upto tridecylamine give clear 1% solutions at 0°. For the higher homologues, increasing chain length of amine in the salt (when K.P. of a homologous series are compared) or nature of the organic acid in the salt (when acetate and propionates of a given alkylamine are compared) means decrease in solubility (increase in K.P.). The results (Table 1) show, however, that increase in chain length of the acid in the salt by one CH₂ group has less effect on K.P. than increasing the chain length of the amine by the same extent. For example, K.P. of tetradecyl amine (12.1°)

increases only to 13.8° when one more CH₂ group is present in acid portion of the salt (tetradecylamine propionate) while it increases to 25.1° when additional CH₂ group is present in the amine portion of the salt (pentadecylamine). The same is true for the higher homologues, but the differences are not significant (Table 1).

Micelle formation: As expected, the CMC decreases as the long alkyl chain of the amine salts increases (Table 1). However, the propionates of amines having odd number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain have higher CMC than the corresponding acetate salts while the reverse trend is true for the salts of amines having even number of C-atoms. This shows that in the organic acid salts of amines, the number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain of the amine as well as the acid chain play a role in micellisation. Unlike for solubility, the effect of presence of additional CH₂ group in the acid portion of the salts is different to that having additional CH₂ group in the amine portion in the behaviour of micelle formation.

The above conclusions are more apparent from the plots of log molar CMC against number of C-atoms in the alkyl chain of amines in the salt (Fig. 2). If odd- and even-chain amine salts are considered as separate homologous surfactant series, with increasing number of C-atoms in the amine

Fig. 2. Plots of log molar CMC and number of C-atoms in the long alkyl chain of alkylamine acetates (ACE) and propionates (PRO).

chains, log molar CMC decreases linearly. However, the plots of the amine propionates of amines with chains of odd number of C-atoms is above that of the corresponding amine acetates while the trend is reversed for the compounds having even number of C-atoms.

The data clearly show that nature of chain length (whether odd or even) of the amine or acid portion of amine salts influences the micellisation in aqueous solutions, and perhaps the intermolecular forces which play a part in affecting the melting behaviour of pure compounds, are also responsible for this behaviour in aqueous solutions.

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